

THE ROLE OF THE PROBLEMS OF THE MEDIA FIELD IN GLOBALIZATION PERIOD

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Abstract. *Today, as we live in a globalized age, we can easily use modern technology. Indeed, today's growing youth can use computer tools without any difficulty. Computer games are also considered to be very useful in developing the potential of the next generation. At the same time, social changes in the global space create certain changes in the content of each nation and various national-territorial units.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies (ICT), PowerPoint, computer games, multimedia. national characteristics, globalization, national identity.*

In the conditions of stable development of the society, in order to protect the public from harmful information and develop national sites, science-based systematic works are being carried out in our country. In multi-ethnic Uzbekistan, it is a historical necessity to instill the feeling of a single motherland in the heart and soul of every citizen. [1, p. 1363–1367]. In this regard, it is appropriate to study the foreign experience of developed countries' Internet networks based on innovative technologies. It should be noted that the number of users of the global Internet network in the world is constantly increasing, while 4.1% of people used the global Internet service 20 years ago, this indicator reached 4.5 billion in 2019, that is, today 58.8% of the population of the Earth uses this information network.

In today's world, when the influence of information on the formation of social opinion and technological development is becoming more and more active, the influence of social networks in this process is increasing day by day. [2, p. 469-473]. Living in modern life, it is very difficult to imagine our life without social networks. We know that today 90% of the world's population can use the Internet easily and without any difficulties. For this reason using social networks, ensuring information protection and security, paying special attention to the issues of data entry, storage, and processing is one of the urgent tasks of the current period. In the world, information technologies and means of mass communication are rapidly gaining importance in the economic, social and spiritual intellectual life of mankind. These priorities show the need to prepare future young teachers for the spiritual and moral education of students by increasing their legal literacy, not only through the formation of competencies in science but also through ideological and legal, and moral competence. [3, p. 415-419].

Social media is not about face-to-face communication, so teenagers and young adults with self-doubt, communication difficulties, and low self-esteem often prefer virtual communication to "live" communication. The social network allows you to learn interesting facts in the field of your interest (literature, art, music, history), exchange educational materials, make purchases, look for or offer a job, solve organizational issues, and find like-minded people. [4, p. 124-125]. People and new friends create communities to share common interests, ideas and experiences, etc. However, it should be remembered that improper use of information, a certain style of maintaining

a personal page, the impossibility of filtering the offered materials, the Internet and social networks can be dangerous, especially for young people. Improving the legal knowledge of members of society in independent Uzbekistan is one of the main conditions for building a legal democratic state. [5, p. 6480-6487].

Today humanity is facing an unusual war. war without any bullets, tanks, weapons but not without victims. The name of this war is known as information war. I liken information warfare to a virus. A bullet can penetrate and injure you from the outside, but the virus does not eat from the inside. If we analyze the processes taking place on the world stage, the difference between the oppressed and the oppressor is determined not by justice, but by who can use the Internet in the mass media. As of today, the number of pages "promoting" spiritual and moral depravity in the social network of the Internet system exceeds several hundred million, which worries humanity even more. Therefore, in the system of social sciences and humanities, in particular in the field of philosophy and sociology, the factor of "self-consciousness" is reflected in the mainstream of the concept of "identity". [6, p. 143-150]. Chingiz Aytmatov writes about this: "It is not necessary to put a camel's skin on the head of a person's destiny." The wars taking place now are not taking place on the battlefield, but in the ideological training ground. From this point of view, it is a great tragedy that young people waste a lot of time on the Internet. Today, more than 90% of the world's population has access to social networks. according to experts' calculations, the minimum time people spend on social networks is 3 hours. Well, a question arises here. How accurate and true information do we get from social networks? What does social networking give us? What are the results of spiritual attacks on the Internet? such global questions have always interested humanity. We live in a time when the Internet is developing rapidly. [7, p. 1360-1363].

It follows from this that every person should strengthen both worldly and religious knowledge at this time, as well as increase his spiritual potential. We know that in every era, along with goodness, evil has been done against it. Therefore, at the moment when the Internet opens up many opportunities, many social attacks are being carried out. What is the reason for this?

I think that today, most young people spend their time not reading books, but spending time with friends on social networks. In such cases, we mainly engage in raising the spiritual consciousness of teenagers and educate them in the spirit of love for books.

In today's era of globalization [8, p.676-688] many young people are eager to learn religion. Unfortunately, this aspect causes many of the young generation to go astray and, at the same time, to live with the label of a traitor. Peace, which is the greatest blessing of God, is not enjoyed by everyone at the same time. If this is the reason, there is a spiritual vacuum in his mind, and the way he supposedly considers to be right for himself has led to the difficulties of many people and even the lives of innocent babies. I'm dying, I'm sorry. Because terrorists are committing unjust bloodshed in different parts of the world. Having opened a cruel battle, retreating to the commandments of the great Lord, he has a heart, "does not understand", eyes, but "does not see", ears, a thousand regrets,

How many innocent people's blossoming lives have been turned into a mess by such executioners who "do not listen" and have completely turned away from faith, or taken prisoners and subjected to torture and humiliation? Can you imagine?

Can humanity be so cruel? What is wrong with children who do not yet know what the path of life is, if they are condemned to death without words? I can't get enough of Sira.

Yes, of course, It is worth [9, p. 1690-1694]. noting that today such attacks and internet attacks have a negative effect on the minds of young people and lead them to wrong paths. it is necessary to approach. Perceiving the society of subscribers as a living organism by the term of this theory, the forecast of the "dead press" of the information society in a negative state is understood. behavior (bullying) provides the anonymity of communication that the Internet provides. Bullying in social networks becomes public, and therefore the consequences for the person who becomes the object of violence are more serious. Due to the anonymity of the Internet, propaganda and hate speech against certain groups or individuals can also spread widely. Often, the behavior of people in the virtual world is completely different from their behavior in real life, because they do not see the reactions of their victims and do not think about the consequences of their actions. Therefore, the Internet is much more vulnerable to human rights violations and defamation. Young people often have access to material that is inappropriate for their age, such as pornography and the promotion of violence. [10, p. 1373-1377]. These social risks require adult attention and prevention.

By the way, day by day, information technologies are covering our lives. They have become an integral part of our daily life, they are used as tools for work, spending time, reducing costs, allocating time for many tasks at the same time, and in general, alleviating the problems of daily life. Undoubtedly, electronic mass media are taking a strong position by fulfilling the main tasks.

We know that, many people believe that the presence of computer games and the Internet has a negative effect on the upbringing and development of the younger generation, and their negative aspects are often studied. But through this article I will try to prove that the positive aspects of computer games and the Internet have a high position in the rise. Computer games do not ignore every growing young child, they have a special place in their life. They expand perception, develop reflexes, stimulate attention to knowledge from school curricula (history, biology, geography, physical education), help to develop the ability to draw conclusions and apply the rules of logic. Using a computer is a similar activity, and it has always been easier to engage a child in a game than to make him learn letters or, say, add numbers, work problems. By playing computer games, the child finds the dreams and desires that exist in his world. This world of technology can be compared to real life.

When the characters of computer games ask the child to fill in the gap, correct the mistakes or arrange the numbers in order to get the treasure, the children feel their importance, learn to remember the necessary, necessary information, order and sequence. At the end of each task, children are praised by the characters of the computer game, that is, "you did it right, you are strong, bless you", it gives the child more enthusiasm and strength. Perfectly drawn for children, full of laughter and professional. convenient, compact, and understandable management, dubbing performed by actors fills each game with joy. [11, p. 5477-5489].

Computer games specially designed for young children are designed to help them imagine certain situations and gain a general understanding of all objects and situations. Thus, the brain of the young generation begins to develop by performing basic thinking operations such as imagining, generalizing and classifying. Computer games teach children to overcome difficulties, control the execution of actions and evaluate the results. , learning to monitor and evaluate is effective by combining in-game and non-game moments. This stage is important for the child. With the help of this game, the child can easily master things that are difficult at first glance, and

he will use all his strength to move to the next level and strive for it. In this, the child will have the ability to use the keyboard and the mouse, and, of course, he will develop an understanding of these technology tools. They get acquainted with basic programs and commands. In addition, the younger generation learns the principles of computer animation and the color palette.

In fact, we know that computer science is taught in schools. In order to find out to what extent children are interested in this, the teachers of each class organize interesting lessons. For example, "Who writes faster?" among young schoolchildren on the computer. "Which student writes incorrectly?" such competitions are held. This also allows students to use computer technologies more correctly and quickly. In addition, with the help of electronic coloring sheets, it is possible to teach the child to recognize colors and master various geometric shapes in the form of electronic puzzles.

Nowadays, I think that every young child understands computer technologies much more than adults and can use them easily without any obstacles. [12, p. 35-42]. Computer games, which are of interest to many children, serve as the most convenient medium for them. There are such computer games, the main theme of which is to prepare the young generation for school. Through computer games, children can acquire information that adults know. [13, p. 469-473]. Also, they can master these topics quickly and easily at their own will. The use of computer games in the daily life of children is of great importance and has an educational effect. They help expand development information.

Let's take a look at some of the opportunities that open up due to computer games:

- Using modified graphic editors, for example, in Paint, allows you to create images of various complexity and gain experience in painting. It will have a great development effect and will have computer creativity. First of all, children describe something on paper and try to transfer it to the computer;

- The use of modified music editors makes it easier for the child to learn notation and be able to use it. It can help in the creation of complex melodies, that is, musical creations.

- Many didactic games are played on a computer. For example, the game "Learning Chess" allows you to organize interesting learning of the game itself.

- Many computer games not only develop children's thinking, but also lead them to spatial imagination. I think that such knowledge is needed in the creation of many projects.

- The 2X game method can also give a child double knowledge. Because in this, various questions and answers are organized to strengthen the subject, and together with this, our national values are introduced.

Yes, of course, everything has its good side and its bad side. We have to take into account such sensitive issues, of course. But we should always be able to use its positive aspects conveniently, quickly and publicly, without being interested in its negative consequences. Therefore, the development of a person [14, p. 113-116] his rise to the level of a human, a mature person, the conflicts and the struggle of contradictions that have arisen during his natural and social activities are always visible before our eyes. It is the person who creates and resolves these contradictions.

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